

A MODERN VIEW OF ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES

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This article examines modern views on the etiology and pathogenesis of periodontal diseases. Diseases of periodontal tissues can develop under the influence of both local causes and the combined influence of local and general factors of exogenous and endogenous origin against the background of altered body reactivity. According to the modern concept, local determinants of periodontal pathology include dental deposits, plaque microorganisms, poor oral hygiene, traumatic occlusion, and anomalies of the anatomical structure of the oral cavity. Common factors of periodontal diseases include deficiencies in vitamins, particularly C, A, D, and E; disorders of metabolism and redox reactions in the body; somatic diseases; and changes in the immunological reactivity of the body.

Keywords: periodontal disease, etiological factors, pathogenesis

Introduction. The high prevalence of periodontal diseases among different population groups worldwide is a complex and unsolved problem today. Diseases of periodontal tissues can develop under the influence of both local causes and the combined influence of local and general factors against the background of altered body reactivity. It should be noted that these factors can be of exogenous and endogenous origin. Their pathogenic influence occurs when they prevail over the protective and adaptive capabilities of the periodontal tissues [1,2].

According to the modern concept, local determinants of periodontal pathology include dental deposits, plaque microorganisms, poor oral hygiene, traumatic occlusion, and anomalies of the anatomical structure of the oral cavity [3].

Aim. Retrospective analysis of professional literary sources devoted to the medically and socially significant topic of periodontal tissue diseases.

Materials and methods. Bibliosemantic and analytical methods were used in the research. An analysis of the professional literature (34 sources) was carried out using information in the scientific-metric databases MEDLINE/PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar.

Results and discussions. According to the WHO expert group, the reason for the development of the inflammatory process in the periodontium is mineralized and non-mineralized dental deposits. Factors contributing to the formation and accumulation of dental plaque include insufficient self-cleaning of the oral cavity (soft food), the nature of food with a predominance of carbohydrates, unsatisfactory oral hygiene care, crowding of teeth, anomalies in the location of teeth, dental rows, overhanging edges of fillings, orthopedic structures, orthodontic appliances, the presence of carious cavities of periapical localization, and quantitative and qualitative changes in oral fluid [4].

Dental plaque bacteria or "microbial biofilm" play a leading role in the development of periodontal disease. Human microbiocenoses differ in the variety of representatives of the microflora. The microflora of

dental plaque is not constant during its existence. As dental plaque accumulates, some opportunistic microorganisms are replaced by others with more pronounced pathogenicity. The usual coccal flora is replaced by a complex consisting of cocci, rods, and spirilla. In inflammatory and inflammatory-dystrophic diseases of the periodontium, gram-negative rods with a high degree of pathogenicity prevail. Gram-negative microorganisms secrete the most aggressive endotoxins, which have a damaging effect on periodontal tissues. The permanent (resident) microbiota of the oral cavity includes streptococci (α and β types), staphylococci, lactobacilli, diphtheroids, saprophytic *Neisseria*, anaerobic cocci (*Peptostreptococcus* and *Peptococcus*), *Veillonella*, *Bacteroides*, *Fusobacterium*, *Leptotrichia*, and spirochetes. Transient microflora is represented by gram-negative anaerobic bacteria, including *E. coli*, bacteria of the genus *Klebsiella*, *Pseudomonas*, *Proteus*, *Clostridium*, and gram-positive bacilli. The main periodontopathogens include *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Treponema denticola*, *Tanarella forsythia*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *Peptostreptococcus*, *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, etc. [5,6,7].

In the oral cavity, there are several protective factors that inhibit the growth of microflora. First of all, it is saliva and oral fluid. The protective function of saliva is associated with immunological and antibacterial properties, which are provided by non-specific and specific mechanisms. Non-specific protection is provided by components of saliva such as lysozyme, lactoperoxidase, lactoferrin, plasma coagulation systems, and the fibrinolytic system of saliva. Specific protection of the oral cavity is carried out by antibodies entering the oral cavity through the epithelial lining, primarily through the attachment epithelium of the gingival sulcus. Secretory IgA, which is secreted by the salivary glands and has an antibacterial effect, prevents the adhesion of microorganisms to the surface of the hard tissues of the teeth [8,9].

Direct penetration of microorganisms into the periodontal tissue can be detected only when the integrity of the epithelial lining is disturbed, as the barrier function of the epithelium is a powerful protective factor. However, when the integrity of the attachment epithelium of the gingival sulcus is violated, entrance gates appear for the penetration of microorganisms into the depth of the connective tissue of the gums. The penetration of bacteria into the periodontal tissue is an important factor in the pathogenesis of inflammatory and dystrophic periodontal diseases. A number of authors note that the active destruction of the alveolar bone and the rapid progression of periodontitis occur precisely during the active penetration of microorganisms into the periodontal tissues. The periodontal tissues are maintained intact as long as the balance between the resistance of the human body and the virulence of the bacteria lasts. A constant chronic inflammatory process in the gums (gingivitis) sooner or later leads to the destruction of the tooth-epithelial attachment and the development of periodontitis [10].

In cases of insufficient oral hygiene, several damaging factors affect the periodontium. Microorganisms accumulate in carious cavities, and the hygienic care of the oral cavity deteriorates. When chewing, the patient reflexively does not use such areas for chewing food, causing overloading of other areas of the dentition. This disturbs the processes of self-cleaning of the oral cavity, and dental deposits accumulate in areas that do not participate in chewing. Carious cavities in the cervical region and on the contact surfaces of the lateral teeth have a particularly adverse effect. The point of contact of the teeth plays a significant role because, on the one hand, it protects the interdental papilla from being injured by food, and on the other hand, it ensures the distribution of the chewing load throughout the entire tooth row. Overhanging edges of fillings, orthopedic and orthodontic structures, as well as structures that overestimate the bite, are also factors in the occurrence of periodontal diseases [11,12].

Common factors of periodontal diseases include deficiencies in vitamins, particularly C, A, and E; disorders of metabolism and redox reactions in the body; somatic diseases; and changes in the immunological reactivity of the body. In cases of generalized periodontitis, there is local hypovitaminosis of vitamin C – despite optimal body saturation with ascorbic acid, its deficiency in periodontal tissues is noted. Both foreign and domestic scientists have found a decrease in the content of vitamins E and A in the blood serum of patients with periodontitis [13,14,15,16].

Periodontal diseases develop against the background of reduced energy metabolism. This is primarily related to the nutritional factor – unbalanced trace element composition, insufficient protein content, and vitamin supply. Recently, lipid peroxidation disorders have been given great importance in the pathogenesis of periodontitis. The main reasons for the activation of non-enzymatic free radical oxidation of lipids in periodontal tissues are: decreased intake of dietary antioxidants (tocopherol, ascorbic acid, bioflavonoids); stresses of various origins; intake of pro-oxidants (pesticides, medicines, nicotine); excessive use of fats;

hypokinesia, leading to low levels of biological oxidation; physical factors (increased radioactive background, ultraviolet radiation, electromagnetic field); age-related decrease in the activity of antioxidant enzymes; congenital enzymopathies of antioxidant enzymes [17,18,19].

Modern medicine has accumulated much clinical evidence of the pathogenetic relationships between diseases of internal organs and lesions of periodontal tissues. The presence of somatic diseases in the human body affects the occurrence and development of periodontal diseases. Combined pathology is characterized by an interconnected course of diseases due to the presence of a multi-link connection between damaged organs. The frequency of periodontal tissue damage in the presence of somatic pathology is directly related to its severity and duration. During exacerbation of the somatic disease, a progressive course of periodontal tissue diseases is observed [20,21,22].

There is a stable relationship between the state of periodontal tissues and endocrine glands, primarily the pancreas, thyroid, parathyroid, gonads, and hypothalamus. Generalized periodontitis against the background of diabetes is characterized by an aggressive course, a tendency to abscess, and more pronounced vascular changes. This is due to the development of microangiopathies characteristic of diabetes, and significant disturbances in metabolic processes lead to a significant decrease in the body's reactivity. The thyroid and parathyroid glands regulate mineral exchange in the body, so when their function is disturbed, resorptive processes in bone tissue are activated [23,24,25].

Numerous studies have proven the pathogenetic commonality of generalized periodontitis and atherosclerosis with damage to the aorta, coronary arteries, and peripheral vessels, and their manifestation against the background of arterial hypertension. In patients with hypertension, a general tendency to vascular sclerosis, spasms, and a decrease in vascular permeability is observed, which is also characteristic of changes in periodontal vessels. Significant hemodynamic disturbances in periodontal tissues are noted during crises [26,27,28,29].

Changes in immunological reactivity of the body in patients with inflammatory and dystrophic forms of periodontal disease are quite common. A decrease in cellular and humoral immunity is observed with inflammatory periodontal diseases, as well as a decrease in the resistance of periodontal tissues to pathogenic bacteria. The immunosuppressive effect is closely related to the processes of metabolic acidosis. The infectious factor in combination with a metabolic disorder leads to persistent chronic inflammation of the gums and a decrease in the resistance of the body [30,31,32].

Conclusion. Periodontal diseases are multifactorial pathologies of infectious-inflammatory origin. Their development depends on local and general factors of exogenous and endogenous origin, against the background of altered body reactivity. Taking into account the large number of factors affecting the periodontal tissue, treatment and preventive measures should be comprehensive and multi-targeted.

References

1. Bandrivsky Yu. L., Vynogradova O. M., Minko L. Yu. Modern aspects of etiopathogenesis of periodontal disease. *European International Journal of Science and Technology*. 2017. № 6(1). P. 44–50.
2. Decker A, Askar H, Tattan M, Taichman R, Wang HL. The assessment of stress, depression, and inflammation as a collective risk factor for periodontal diseases: a systematic review. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2020; 24(1):1-12. doi:10.1007/s00784-019-03089-3.
3. Sculean A. Editorial: Common risk factors for dental caries and periodontal diseases. *Oral Health Prev Dent*. 2017. Vol. 15(1). P. 5.
4. Shevchuk M. M. Modern concepts of etiology and pathogenesis of inflammatory periodontal diseases. *The Pharma Innov. J*. 2018. Vol. 7, N. 6. P. 170–173.
5. Rocca JP, Fornaini C, Wang Z, Tan L, Merigo E. Focal infection and periodontitis: a narrative report and new possible approaches. *Int J Microbiol*. 2020;8875612 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8875612>
6. Graves DT, Corrêa JD, Silva TA. The Oral Microbiota Is Modified by Systemic Diseases. *J Dent Res*. 2019;98(2):148-156. doi:10.1177/0022034518805739
7. Denefil O, Chorniy S, Boitsaniuk S, Manashchuk N, Chornij N, Levkiv M, et al. Analysis of microbiocenosis of a gingival sulcus and periodontal pockets of patients with periodontal diseases associated with systemic pathology. *Explor Med*. 2023;4:942–55 <https://doi.org/10.37349/emed.2023.00186>
8. Abusleme L, Dupuy AK, Dutzan N, Silva N, Burleson JA, Strausbaugh LD, et al. The subgingival microbiome in health and periodontitis and its relationship with community biomass and inflammation. *ISME J*. 2013;7:1016–25.
9. Benachinmardi KK, Nagamoti J, Kothiwale S, Metgud SC. Microbial flora in chronic periodontitis: study at a tertiary health care center from North Karnataka. *J Lab Physicians*. 2015 Jan-Jun; 7 (1): 49-54.
10. Hajishengallis G. Periodontitis: from microbial immune subversion to systemic inflammation. *Nat Rev Immunol*. 2015;15(1):30-44.
11. Kwon T, Lamster IB, Levin L. Current Concepts in the Management of Periodontitis. *Int Dent J*. 2021 Dec;71(6):462-476. doi: 10.1111/idj.12630. Epub 2021 Feb 19. PMID: 34839889
12. Elkerbout TA, Slot DE, Rijnen ME, van der Weijden GAF. Change in oral hygiene behaviour after non-surgical periodontal therapy - A retrospective analyses. *Int J Dent Hyg*. 2023 Feb;21(1):259-271. doi: 10.1111/idh.12593. Epub 2022 Apr 11. PMID: 35286771
13. Goldstein M. R., Mascitelli L. Periodontitis, atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease and vitamin D. *Am. J. Cardiol*. 2009. Vol. 15 (8). P. 1164.
14. Gutierrez Gossweiler A, Martinez-Mier EA. Chapter 6: Vitamins and Oral Health. *Monogr Oral Sci*. 2020;28:59-67. doi: 10.1159/000455372. Epub 2019 Nov 7. PMID: 31940621 Review.
15. Botelho J, Machado V, Proença L, Delgado AS, Mendes J. Vitamin D Deficiency and Oral Health: A Comprehensive Review. *J.Nutrients*. 2020 May 19;12(5):1471. doi: 10.3390/nu12051471. PMID: 32438644
16. Ustianowski Ł, Ustianowska K, Gurazda K, Rusiński M, Ostrowski P, Pawlik A. The Role of Vitamin C and Vitamin D in the Pathogenesis and Therapy of Periodontitis-Narrative Review. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2023 Apr 5;24(7):6774. doi: 10.3390/ijms24076774. PMID: 37047746
17. Chapple I. L., Matthews J. B. The role of reactive oxygen and antioxidant species in periodontal tissue destruction. *Periodontol 2000*. 2007. Vol. 43. P. 160–232.
18. Veljovic T, Djuric M, Mirnic J, Gusic I, Maletin A, Ramic B, Neskovic I, Vukoje K, Brkic S. Lipid Peroxidation Levels in Saliva and Plasma of Patients Suffering from Periodontitis. *J Clin Med*. 2022 Jun 23;11(13):3617. doi: 10.3390/jcm11133617. PMID: 35806902 Free PMC article
19. Mohideen K, Chandrasekar K, Ramsridhar S, Rajkumar C, Ghosh S, Dhungel S. Assessment of Oxidative Stress by the Estimation of Lipid Peroxidation Marker Malondialdehyde (MDA) in Patients with Chronic Periodontitis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Int J Dent*. 2023 May 30;2023:6014706. doi: 10.1155/2023/6014706. eCollection 2023.
20. Bui FQ, Almeida-da-Silva CLC, Huynh B, et al. Association between periodontal pathogens and systemic disease. *Biomed J*. 2019; 42(1):27-35. doi:10.1016/j.bj.2018.12.001
21. Martínez-García M, Hernández-Lemus E. Periodontal Inflammation and Systemic Diseases: An Overview. *Front Physiol*. 2021;12:709438 doi: 10.3389/fphys.2021.709438
22. Zhang Y, Qiao D, Chen R, Zhu F, Gong J, Yan F. The association between periodontitis and inflammatory bowel disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Biomed Res Int*. 2021:6692420. doi: 10.1155/2021/6692420.
23. Fabue LC, Soriano Y J, Pérez MGS. Dental management of patients with endocrine disorders. *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Dentistry*. 2010;2(4):196–203.
24. Cardoso L. F. The multiple effects of thyroid disorders on bone and mineral metabolism. *Arq. Bras. Endocrinol. Metab*. 2014; 58(5): 452–463.
25. Liccardo D, Cannavo A, Spagnuolo G, Ferrara N, Cittadini A, Rengo C, Rengo G. Periodontal Disease: A Risk Factor for Diabetes and Cardiovascular Disease. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2019 Mar 20;20(6):1414. doi: 10.3390/ijms20061414.
26. Xu S, Song M, Xiong Y, Liu X, He Y, Qin Z. The association between periodontal disease and the risk of myocardial infarction: a pooled analysis of observational studies. *BMC Cardiovasc Disord*. 2017;17(1):50 doi:10.1186/s12872-017-0480-y
27. Cho D-H, Song In-S, Choi J, Gwon JG. Risk of peripheral arterial disease in patients with periodontitis: A nationwide, population-based, matched cohort study. *Research Article*. 2020;297:96-101. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2020.02.012>
28. Oberoi S, Harish Y, Hiremath S, Puranik M. A cross-sectional survey to study the relationship of

periodontal disease with cardiovascular disease, respiratory disease, and diabetes mellitus. *J. Indian Soc. Periodontol.* 2016. Vol.20(4). P. 446–452.

29. Hwan Byun S, Min Ch, Jin Hong S, Geun Choi H, Hee Koh D. Analysis of the Relation between Periodontitis and Chronic Gastritis/Peptic Ulcer: A Cross-Sectional Study Using KoGES HEXA Data. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020; 17(12): 4387 doi: 10.3390/ijerph17124387.

30. Gheorghe DN, Foia L, Toma V, Surdu A, Herascu E Hepatitis C Infection and Periodontal Disease: Is there a Common Immunological Link? *J Immunol Res.* 2018 Mar 13;2018:8720101. doi: 10.1155/2018/8720101. eCollection 2018.

31. De Molon RS, Rossa C Jr, Thurlings RM, Cirelli JA, Koenders MI. Linkage of Periodontitis and

Rheumatoid Arthritis: Current Evidence and Potential Biological Interactions. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2019; 20(18). P. 4541.

32. Farzin M, Derafshi R, Ghapanchi J, Kafsh AZ, Rezaiee M. Oral manifestations of hypertension and rheumatic heart disease: a cross sectional study in elderly patients. *Asian Journal of Medical and Pharmaceutical Researches.* 2016. Vol. 6(2). P. 9-13.

33. Cardoso EM, Reis C, Manzanares-Céspedes MC. Chronic periodontitis, inflammatory cytokines, and interrelationship with other chronic diseases. *Postgrad. Med.* 2018 Jan; 130 (1): 98-104.

34. Cavalla F, Letra A, Silva RM, Garlet GP. Determinants of Periodontal/Periapical Lesion Stability and Progression. *J Dent Res.* 2021 Jan;100(1):29-36. doi: 10.1177/0022034520952341. Epub 2020 Aug 31